

Students' Awareness of the Use of Poster, Power Point and Animated Video Presentations: A Case Study of Third Year Students of the Department of English of Batna University

Bahloul Amel

Abstract—The present study debates students' perceptions of the use of technology in learning English as a Foreign Language. Its aim is to explore and understand students' preparation and presentation of Posters, PowerPoint and Animated Videos by drawing attention to visual and oral elements. The data is collected through observations and semi-structured interviews and analyzed through phenomenological data analysis steps. The themes emerged from the data, visual learning satisfaction in using information and communication technology, providing structure to oral presentation, learning from peers' presentations, draw attention to using Posters, PowerPoint and Animated Videos as each supports visual learning and organization of thoughts in oral presentations.

Keywords—Animated Videos, EFL, Posters, PowerPoint presentations, Visual Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the world of science and technology, the most lasting educational impact comes from having students use of technology to create products and experiences for connections with one another and using knowledge comfortably [8]. Designing and communicating information requires language learners to deepen their understanding of content while increasing visual, sound, oral language, creativity and thinking skills [5]. However, what matters most is to explore which tools address to students' application in language learning. PowerPoint, Poster and video, one of the web-based tools in the entire world of Web 2.0, are among the tools that can be used for educational purposes.

Poster, one of the tools used in language learning, is defined as a well-illustrated paper prepared to educate [13]. It presents a comprehensible approach combining visual expertise. Poster also requires an awareness of using visual language well [29]. The other tool, PowerPoint is generally believed that the use of it facilitated students' learning. Finally, Video is designed with a constructivist approach encouraging students to navigate, create, and construct their knowledge. It offers an interactive environment that allows students to design learning, to be creative by constructing their own learning experiences. In addition, it is a free program mixing students' images and music together to create music

videos. Language learners can create unlimited videos for themselves and share them with their friends, which brings their lessons to life. They can post videos to video sharing sites like YouTube, TeacherTube, etc..., or download them for in-class presentations.

As Poster and PowerPoint are used in many professions, there are many studies focusing on designing and presenting Poster and PowerPoint, mentioned in many contexts such as nursing, medicine [34]. Also, Poster and PowerPoint are used for variety of purposes in language teaching in learning [34]. However as it seems there is no study that provides a guide for using animated videos in language learning and comparing animated videos to Poster and PowerPoint that most students have experience of preparation and presentation [8].

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The purpose of this qualitative study is to examine experiences of students in Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos. Based on phenomenological [15] theoretical framework, the following research questions will guide this present study:

- 1- What are university students' experiences of learning English as a Foreign Language while presenting :
 - a- Poster?
 - b- PowerPoint?
 - c- Animated Video?
- 2- What are the differences and similarities among Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video as language learning materials?

III. POSTER, POWERPOINT AND ANIMATED VIDEO IN EFL

Learning is a constructive activity that the students themselves have to carry out [39]. Learning activities in constructivist settings are characterized by active engagement, inquiry, problem solving, and collaboration with others. From this point of view, then, the task of the educator is not to dispense knowledge but provide students with opportunities and incentives to build it up [39]. Students can create or construct their own understandings or knowledge through the interaction of what they already know and the activities such as Poster, PowerPoint and Animated videos which they come in contact.

Bahloul Amel is with the University of Batna, Algeria (e-mail: bahloul_amel@yahoo.fr).

A. Poster

In the past decade, there has been a tremendous shift toward communicative language instruction. In the classroom, communicative language teaching takes on many forms. The most successful communicative classrooms are indeed those that take the students' interest into consideration and those that are more authentic in nature. Poster presentations are increasingly used by many professions for many purposes [29]. They are mentioned in many contexts, such as nursing, chemistry, and medicine. Posters have also become part of day-to-day environment of Teaching and Learning English as a Foreign Language.

Poster presentations can be used to help university students further develop their communicative skills in the target language and to help them investigate content areas of personal interest [17]. According to [29], Poster presentation is important as it can reflect many impressions about you as an individual or the institution / department that you represent. Poster sessions in the classroom have linguistic and content aims, which can help students to present their materials successfully. Linguistic aims are "to develop fluency in English, to improve vocabulary in a particular content area, to see the value of using English as a vehicle for communication, to improve research, reading and presentation skills, to appreciate the English language" [15]. Content aims are to "understand a certain content area in more detail, to investigate something that is of real interest, to have a desire to present research findings and to have a feeling of accomplishment" [15]. It is important to educate students about both scientific and non-scientific presentation types [34]. Both conference presentations and Posters use verbal and visual languages in these presentation types. The difference in emphasis between the two modes is: presentations rely primarily on verbal literacy to convey meaning, while Posters rely primarily on visual literacy to convey meaning.

As Posters are a special type of presentation, they need to be well designed. Major principles of Poster design are to define aims and objectives, and to consider the target audience, which determine the style of poster. As space in Poster can be limited, the selection of materials and information that represents the subject gains importance. For example, "one good photograph may say more than several mediocre ones; one good illustration may demonstrate a point more clearly than a lengthy description [29]. The organization of the subject and material can help the audience follow the poster easily.

B. PowerPoint

PowerPoint is rapidly "becoming the de facto instructional tool in secondary and higher education, though its increase in popularity has been mirrored by increased criticism from a "pedagogical perspective"[32]. Almost many secondary schools and universities are embracing the use of PowerPoint presentations in the classroom. Researchers have examined how helpful PowerPoint presentations are. Studies have consistently indicated that students generally believed that the use of PowerPoint facilitated their learning [1].

Several studies focus on the idea that pictures, graphs, maps, tables improve students' recall [6]. Pictures should be relevant to and enhance the meaning of the text [4]. According to [9], the students have reacted very positively to the visual elements because they can see what is discussing. By using PowerPoint, all materials are organized in one place. It is possible to flip among slides that students wish to see again. Students can comment about their heightened level of interest because they can see the places, people, and events as described. PowerPoint can be beneficial, but material that is not pertinent to the presentation can be harmful to students' learning [4].

As one of the multimedia presentations, PowerPoint can be as simple as having only text on a colored screen. Presentations can also be complex with tables, pictures, graphs, sound and visual effect, video clips, etc. The effectiveness of PowerPoint and other multimedia presentations may depend on the complexity of the presentation. In fact, several researchers have demonstrated that material such as irrelevant sounds [26], interesting but extraneous text [35], and "irrelevant pictures" [23] can reduce comprehension, but all materials in PowerPoint should reflect the educational purpose of the presentation.

C. Animated Videos

Although Poster and PowerPoint presentations are generally used for foreign language learning by University students in Algeria, the idea of using animated videos is new to them. Animated videos are designed with a constructivist approach encouraging students to navigate, create, and construct their knowledge. For most educationists, constructivism offers far more scope for realizing the possible learning benefits of using information and communication technology [2]. Similarly, many writers have expressed the hope that constructivism will lead to better educational software and better learning [16]. Reference [11] states that some educationists stress the need for open-ended exploratory authentic learning environments in which learners can develop personally meaningful and transferable knowledge and understanding. As noted, Animated Videos offer an interactive environment that allows students to design learning, to be creative by constructing their own learning experiences. Only in complex and rich environments will learners have the opportunity to reconstruct concepts in idiosyncratic and personally meaningful ways [11].

As constructivist theory focusses on making connections and making meaning in the learning process, it enables language learners, teachers and all researchers to take advantages of the web-based developments. Language learners can each have their own accounts to make full-length videos while in class and at home, they can also download their videos. This makes both in-class and homework assignments easier to do as long as there is an internet connection. Language learners can create unlimited videos for themselves and also share them with their friends, which is the most significant feature of Animated Videos. They can post videos

wherever they want to download them for in-class presentations.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants of the Study

Ten third year (LMD) students from the Department of English of Batna University – Algeria were designed to participate in this study. The participants ranged in age from 22 to 25 years with the varying level of experience in preparing and presenting both Poster and PowerPoint, but none of them claimed to be familiar with Animated Videos. The participants of the study had been actively engaged in Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos activities, and were willing to participate in this study and discuss their experiences.

B. Data Collection Procedures

The data were collected through semi-structured interviews [19] and archival documents; Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos. Three semi-structured interviews, each lasting 30 minutes were conducted with each participant about Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos preparation and presentation in language learning. The Participants' Poster and PowerPoint presentations can contact with the researchers. This qualitative study consists of three presentation types: Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos. The presentations of all the participants follow this order: 1st week, Poster – 2nd week, PowerPoint – 3rd week, Animated Videos. The subjectivity statements of each participant on Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos were taken just before the instruction of the related activity. During the presentations, Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos evaluation criteria were used to help them evaluate their works. After each Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video presentation, semi-structured interviews were conducted with each participant about their awareness in the use of the related activities Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video.

C. Data Analysis

The data in the present study were analyzed through phenomenological data analysis steps [27] after audio-recorded semi-structured interviews and video-recorded oral presentations were transcribed. During this analysis process, [15] theoretical framework, "What students' experiences of learning English as a Foreign Language while presenting Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos are" and "What the differences and similarities among Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos as language learning materials are" were described and identified.

V. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

As revealed from archival documents and semi-structured interviews with participants, themes with supporting quotes were presented. The data analysis approach adopted for this research followed [27] approach and the phenomenon planning, preparing and presenting Poster, PowerPoint and

Animated Videos was experienced in the following themes considering the research questions of the study:

A. Theme One: Satisfaction in Using PowerPoint and Animated Videos

The first theme that emerges from the semi-structured interviews was the students' having Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos experiences and the satisfaction in using them. All the participants have participated in Poster and PowerPoint presentations as a presenter and a listener but none of them has experienced Animated Videos. After the presentations were finished, the participants had a sense of accomplishment and learned the skill of making Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos presentations. Poster presentations can help students further their communicative skills and gives them confidence to speak in the Foreign language but all participants find hard to prepare Poster. Also, they found organizing the topic in their mind during Poster presentations difficult. For example, Salima's Poster experience in the following highlights the theme:

"Planning and preparing Poster is really difficult. You need to organize well. If not, it makes listeners' understanding the topic hard."

Similarly, Wafa stated:

"While I am designing Poster, I have some difficulties. It has to reflect the topic. It should be designed in such a way that when I am not near my Poster, It should reflect the topic on its own clearly."

In Literature, some researchers have found that PowerPoint enhances students' academic performance [20], [21], [38], whereas others have found no effect [7], [18], [33]. For the actual presentation, [36] recommends practice as the best way to prepare and increase the odds of success.

B. Theme Two: Visual Learning

From earliest times, people have used visual displays to communicate. Visual learning is a powerful teaching tool, both for kids who are natural visual learners, and for children with limited language proficiency [28]. It is about making sense of complex information quickly and being able to comprehend ideas at glance. Visual learning plays a key role in providing the structure for organizing information. From the choice of colors to the selection of illustrations, all can make the information accessible. In Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos, visual cues fully engaged in all participants as they supported their presentations. 'Mohamed' described it:

"When we looked at as visual aids, it is a good tool. It can be also used in foreign language learning"

'Nawel' made the point clearly by saying that *"Animated Video is a strong visual aid. You see the pictures, match them with the music and at that time, you never forget it."*

'Nesrine' echoed that *"If I have done my PowerPoint presentation without visuals, I do not think that it would take attention as it was."*

It appeared that visual indicators draw attention to the points of interest and help Foreign Language Learners.

Especially, Animated Videos engaged visual learners in an environment that they feel more comfortable.

Meanwhile, it has been shown that children acquire speech perception in their L1 through dependence on visual signals from their caretakers [24]. When visual and auditory signals do not coincide, there are great number of incidences of blended mishearing [22]. 'Nesrine' described the visual auditory aids when she said: *"The audience listened me carefully and watched the images. I think it became effective. They could associate them in their minds."*

'Malak' also added: *"I generally understand better when something is taught visually. It also makes learning easy."*

By representing information specially and with images, students are able to focus on meaning, recognize and group similar ideas easily, make better use of their visual memory [3]. According to the present study, the participants remember information better when it is represented and learned both visually and verbally. Although there is a strong evidence that visual aids used in Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos enhance students' learning of English, [37] claimed that the pictures used in PowerPoint are less clear about whether it is beneficial for student's academic performance.

C. Theme Three: Providing Structure to Oral Presentation

When discussed from teachers' or lectures' perspective, prior studies claim that PowerPoint enhances teachers' ability to order and pace lectures [14]. Like teachers' perspective on this theme, learners perceive that the Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video's main feature is to provide structure to their presentations in the class. Some say that PowerPoint's actual popularity is rooted in that most people are terrified of public presentation and PowerPoint gives them a handrail to cling to [30]. Because the slides are organized in a reasonable order beforehand, PowerPoint can make students' presentation easier as they do not have to think about the order of the presentation. Thus, 'Mohamed' commented: *"I can reflect the organization in PowerPoint better because there is a certain order in PowerPoint but there is not in Poster. Listeners or observers choose firstly what they want to see or hear but it is not like that in PowerPoint."*

As reflected in the above, 'Safa' also shared the same idea: *"During PowerPoint an Animated video presentations, I do not have to compose an order in my mind. As there is an order in both, I presented them more relaxed. Everything was in order."*

Students can use diagrams to display large amounts of information in ways that are easy to understand and help reveal relationships and patterns. Reference [36] also says he cannot stress enough that a disorganized presentation with PowerPoint is still a disaster; and, similarly, an organized presentation without PowerPoint is still a success. The students' enhanced self-efficacy may have been driven by their perception that PowerPoint presentations were better structured [38] and emphasized the key points better [10], [38].

D. Theme Four: Learning from Peers' Presentations

A related benefit was that, by viewing the presentations of their classmates, "Students had an opportunity to learn at least a little bit about all of the topics researched, not just about their own. All but one student indicated in the survey that they enjoyed seeing the other students' presentations" [31]. The following quote by 'Rania' exemplifies participants' learning from other presentations:

"The others did very impressive activities, but I couldn't have done. I learned all from them. I will do them in my other presentations... Listeners have knowledge about drama activities and they learn how to prepare them."

Reference [25] argued that sharing power in the evaluation process would ease the stress many students experience about taking the risk of presenting their ideas during a course of study. They argued that such stress is associated with hierarchical model of higher education teaching where the professor is seen as the front of all knowledge and the arbiter of learning so that there is a certain amount of tension associated with students presenting arguments that might be wrong [12]. According to [25], freedom from teacher judgment provided a space for each student to feel more comfortable about knowledging and valuing her thinking and publicly presenting her knowledge. In this study, as the researcher was not their teacher, they felt relax during all their presentations. Even 'Safa' revealed by saying: *"I used to have my PowerPoints, prepare my friends because I was thinking, if I made a mistake, teachers would get angry, and get low scores. But with this experience, I learned that I can do all of them even without my friends."*

Reference [36] suggests asking trusted colleagues who can be counted on to give constructive feedback to sit through a presentation so that the presenter can move from side to side and increase his or her confidence in the presentation.

VI. IMPLICATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Even though Poster and PowerPoint are widely used for Foreign Language Learning and teaching materials, the studies on Poster and PowerPoint presentations are mostly examined from the teachers' perspective. The current study comparing foreign language learners' presentations of Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video, a brand new activity for Algerian students, highlights the gap by investigating from learners' viewpoint with phenomenological approach. In addition, there is no empirical research that specifically targets Animated Videos as a foreign language learning material. This study can guide and make students foreign language learning material preferences easy considering the features of Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video. Future empirical studies might look at broader spectrum of students' experiences. Also, further studies especially on Animated Videos, may be worthwhile to question the recorded oral presentations rather face to face to face presentations.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study used the qualitative methodology of phenomenology to gather rich texts on the complex topic of Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos. The contribution of the qualitative findings of this study completes the existing gap on the application of the foreign language learning tools presented in this study. The goal of this research was to contribute to the field in the use of Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos by providing an understanding of the experience of third year students of English of Batna University. The quality of the findings from this research lies in the resulting comprehensive picture of those students' experiences, which illuminate areas of planning, preparing, and presenting of Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Videos, and guide for students, teachers and researchers. Also, the findings of this study can be limited in its ability to be generalized. It is recommended that a further research can be conducted, building on this study. From the phenomenological approach used here, valuable insights supporting on the use of Poster, PowerPoint and Animated Video as a brand new web-based tool used in Algeria, can be derived.

REFERENCES

- [1] Apperson, J. M., Laws, E. L., & Scepanky, J. A. (2006). The impact of presentation graphics on students' experience in the classroom. *Computers and Education*, 47(1), 116-126.
- [2] Atkins, M. J. (1993). Theories of Learning and multimedia applications: an overview. *Research Papers in Education*, 8(2), 251-271.
- [3] Bartoletti, R. (2008, July 25). How Good Visual Design Helps Learning. Retrieved from the connexions Web site: <http://cnx.org/content/m17294/1.4/>
- [4] Bartsh, R. A., and Cobern, K. M. (2003). Effectiveness of PowerPoint presentation in lectures. *Computers & Education*, 41, 77-86.
- [5] Celce-Murcia, M. (2001). *Teaching English as a Second or Foreign Language*. Heinle&Heinle.
- [6] Chanlin, L. J. (2000). Attributes of animation for learning scientific knowledge. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 27, 228-238.
- [7] Daniels, L. (1999). Introducing technology in the classroom. PowerPoint as a first step. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 10, 42-56.
- [8] Davis, C., & Davis, J. (2005). Using technology to create a sense of community. *English Journal*, 94(6), 36-41.
- [9] Dinan, S. E. (2000). Technology in the classroom: Microsoft PowerPoint slide shows. *The Sixteenth Century Journal*, 31(2), 453-455.
- [10] Frey, B. A., & Bimbaum, D. J. (2002). Learners perceptions on the value of PowerPoint in lectures. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburg (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED467192).
- [11] Harper, B., Squires, D. and McDougall, A. (2000). Constructivist Simulations in the Multimedia Age. *Journal of Educational Multimedia and Hypermedia*, 9(2), 115-130.
- [12] Heron, J. (1981). Assessment revisited. In D. Boud (Ed.), *Developing student autonomy in learning*. London: Kogan Page.
- [13] Hesketh, E. A. & Harden, R. M. (1994). An interactive poster display. *Journal of Audiovisual Media in Medicine*, 17, 137-138.
- [14] Hlynka, D. & Mason, R. (1998). PowerPoint in the classroom: What is the point?. *Educational Technology*, 38, 45-48.
- [15] Husserl, E. (1931). *Ideas: General Introduction to Pure Phenomenology*. London: George Allan & Unwin.
- [16] Jonassen, D. H. (1994). Thinking technology: Toward a constructivist design model. *Educational Technology*, 34(3), 34-37.
- [17] Jost, N. (2005). Poster presentations and language teaching. *JALT2004 Conference Proceedings*. Tokyo: JALT.
- [18] Kask, S. (2000, January). The impact of using computer presentations (CAP) on students learning in the microeconomics principles course. Paper presented at the meeting of the American Economic Association, Boston.
- [19] Kvale, S. (1996). *InterViews: An Introduction to Qualitative Research Interviewing*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [20] Lowry, R. B. (1999). Electronic presentation of lectures effect upon student performance. *University Chemistry Education*, 3, 18-21.
- [21] Mantei, E. J. (2000). Using internet class notes and PowerPoint in the physical geology lecture. *Journal of College Science Teaching*, 29, 301-305.
- [22] Massaro, D. (1994). *Psychological aspects of speech perception: Handbook of psycholinguistics*. New York: Academic Press.
- [23] Mayer, R. E. (2001). *Multimedia learning*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- [24] McGurk, H. & MacDonald, J. W. (1976). Hearing lips and seeing voices. *Nature*, 264, 746-748.
- [25] McVarich, J., & Solloway, S. (2002). Self-evaluation: creating a classroom without unhealthy competitiveness. *Educational Forum*, 66, 253-260.
- [26] Moreno, R. & Meyer, R. E. (2000). A coherence effect in multimedia learning : the case for minimizing irrelevant sounds in the design of multimedia instructional messages. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 92, 117-125.
- [27] Moustakas, C. (1994). *Phenomenological Research Methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [28] Murphy, S. J. (2005). *Visual Learning, Children and Math*. 63 Books, Pre-k through Grade 4. Retrieved from <http://www.stuartjmurphy.com/>
- [29] Murray, R., Thow, M., & Strachan, R. (1998). Visual Literacy: Designing and Presenting a Poster. *Physiotherapy*, 84(7), 319-327.
- [30] Naughton, J. (2003). How PowerPoint can fatally weaken your argument. Retrieved from <http://observer.guardian.co.uk/business/story/0,6903,1110963,00>. Html. Accessed December 06, 2009.
- [31] Perry, A. E. (2003). PowerPoint Presentations: A creative addition to the research process. *The English Journal*, 92(6), 64-69.
- [32] Price, C. B. (2008). Unreal PowerPoint: Immersing PowerPoint presentations in virtual computer game engine world. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24, 2486-2495.
- [33] Rankin, E. L. & Hoas, D. J. (2001). The use of PowerPoint and student performance. *Atlantic Economic Journal*, 29, 113.
- [34] Rush, K, Merritt-Gray, M. and Noel, J. (1995). The poster assignment: A connected teaching strategy for increasing student comfort with issues of sexuality. *Nurse Education Today*, 15, 298-302.
- [35] Schraw, G. (1998). Processing and recall differences among seductive details. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90, 3-12.
- [36] Stein, K. (2006). The Dos and Don'ts of PowerPoint Presentations. *Journal of the American Dietetic Associations*, 10, 1745 - 1748.
- [37] Susskind, J. E. (2008). Limits of PowerPoint's Power: Enhancing students' self-efficacy and attitudes but not their behavior. *Computers & Education*, 50, 1228-1239.
- [38] Szabo, A. & Hastings, N. (2000). Using IT in the undergraduate classroom: should we replace the blackboard with PowerPoint? *Computers and Education*, 35, 175-187.
- [39] Von Glasserfeld, E. (2005). *Constructivism: Theory, Perspectives and Practice*. London: Falmer.